

IMPORTANCE OF CRITICAL THINKING IN BOTH SOCIETY AND EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The research work talks about critical thinking, which is considered a special type of thinking, and its relevance is cited on the basis of facts. There has also been talk of how critical thinking is achieved. After reading the article, it can be seen that the importance of critical thinking is important not only in the field of education, but also in their further professional activities.*

Key words: *Socrates doctrine, Thomas Jefferson, stages of critical thinking, advantages of critical thinking.*

The 21st century is an information age, so every day we come across different information. This information is shared by young people it has a positive or negative effect on consciousness, depending on their perception. Distributed information is correct by young people in order to be evaluated and accepted, it is necessary that young people have developed the ability to think critically. So critical thinking is becoming relevant for those who live in the information age. Critical thinking, especially in a student, is time-consuming. Hence for the use of methods that promote critical thinking in the educational system is a period requirement. Critical thinking is thinking that a separate type relies on the facts to deduce the calculation. Critical thinking is finding someone's disadvantage, criticizing not, but rather a form of self-correcting, self-governing thinking.

If we look at history, the roots of critical thinking can be traced back to Socrates' teaching practice 2,500 years ago can be observed. He emphasized reasoning for clarity and logical consistency, and his method has the definition of "Socratic interrogation boldi. However, by this time, this definition has changed, and this is the process of thinking to decide what to believe or what to do began to realize. Obviously, our future depends on information, technology and innovation, from readers it requires a quick and effective solution of problems using critical thinking skills. From critical thinking use intellectual such as conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating information to students allows the use of tools. In short, it is the process of analyzing facts to make judgments. In education, teachers use effective, successful methods to develop students' critical

thinking skills must use. Not only should students have critical thinking during their years of education, but this thinking ability they will also need it for the next life process.

In addition, critical thinking can be found independently in books, well-known journals, academic journals can be developed by reading. As US President Thomas Jefferson noted, an educated citizen is important for our survival as a free people is a condition. According to his perception, only critical thinkers see the entirety of the evidence, resulting in spiritual maturity in society citizens can mature. So critical thinkers try to be more open to different views and want to know more by constantly asking questions. They never have anything at face value, maybe they know how to understand based on a situation or concept. At the same time, they are able to make decisions, think logically and they can develop other important skills, such as creative thinking. Being a creative thinker is not only for learning, but also important for their vital process.

When people graduate from school or higher education, their criticism the ability to think expands and grows there. The critical thinking of young people develops in the educational field. Including a variety of elementary grades mathematical operations are of educational importance, which are given to the young house as a task, as well as fairy tales and stories their independent, critical and logical thinking process continues to develop in stages. To critical thinking to achieve, the following steps must be passed:

1. Evaluate new information The first step in critical thinking is to accept information only after evaluating it. What is read or heard whether, critical thinkers seek to find objective reality. In

this, the students are able to deal with possible problems and solutions are evaluated by review. The process of obtaining new information and reviewing the results is called evaluation.

2. Consider the source Next, if the reader is receiving information, he should understand where it comes from. For example, if new information comes from advertising, it is clear that advertising is a marketing technique designed to sell a product understanding can help assess potential bias. Every information you receive is given to you by someone who has the motivation to share knowledge. Critical students with abilities evaluate the source taking into account the motivation to provide information.

3. Ask a lot of questions Asking questions is an important skill if you are trying to improve your critical thinking skills. When the information is presented, you need to decide what questions will help you better assess it. Some examples: In what ways can this problem be solved? Who provides this information? Why is this information being provided? What other prospects are there on this topic? What are the studies on this issue?

4. Follow up with research Before you form your own opinion with the help of critical thinking, you need to do research yourself. To the answer once you've come up with a list of questions you need, you can use resources like the Internet. If you think you prefer online information, syndicated news sites, educational institutions, and non-profit look for authoritative information from sources such as organizations. Other options are to use sources such as encyclopedias or it is also possible to review the materials in your local library.

5. Opinion formation With answers to critical questions, you can form your own opinion. At this stage, you can draw your own opinion you can be sure that you are based on logical, factual information, because you are guided by the stages of critical thinking you've done it.

Below we will get acquainted with the advantages of critical thinking: 1. This will help improve decision making Critical thinking allows you to make decisions yourself. This in turn makes decision-making helps to improve. This critical thinking ability is used by students not to complicate any situation and the solution to it it must be developed to help find. 3. Improve your

research ability Critical thinking improves your research skills, in addition, each to achieve a good result it helps to accurately research the aspect by observing, analyzing, synthesizing and experimenting in detail. 4. Bleaches your creativity This will help polish your creative side. Creativity is undoubtedly a modern worker in collaboration defines himself as the necessary skill of his strength. Critical thinking will definitely polish your creativity. 5. Encourages interest Finding the right solution for the problem or the topic you are working on will arouse interest in you. Interest is better for you allows deeper research and study to achieve the result. This factor allows you to become a lifelong reader.

As you can witness, critical thinking is not only in the field of education, but also in society, in the future workplace of students also plays an important roll. Thinking critically at work, coming up with a great perspective that can lead to an impressive decision or problem-solving means sorting out useful details for. "Critical thinking helps students develop competencies that serve them throughout their professional life helps" - Dunlap, Van Liere, mertig and Jones. (2000) 20 percent of critical thinking skills in early childhood or 5 in a survey conducted by foreign experts it develops best during the underage period. Another 35 percent of critical thinking is best between the ages of 6 and 12 it says it has developed and another 27% believe it is best between the ages of 13 and 18. About 13 percent of all ages they say it is good for developing critical thinking skills.

As I mentioned above, we read books, daily magazines instead of giving our children gadgets for their hands we have to force. To discuss and understand what we read and to verify critical thinking we need to have time to ask for their opinions. We provide our children financially, but in this life, we do not provide the necessary spirituality to find a place. If they do not have the ability to think critically, they do not understand the meaning of life. Even if there is a small problem in his life, he will be depressed it is possible, and this, in turn, leads to bad consequences. Or get used to bad habits that waste his life it is unlikely to remain. In my opinion, the inclusion of religious knowledge and

faith-strengthening disciplines in the educational program both have a positive effect on young people, and they do not fall under the influence of all sorts of destructive ideas coming from the internet. Conclusion. In a rapidly changing and fast digital age, it is very important to have critical thinking skills. This is the current finding

oneself in the information age is, in other words, preserving the future of our youth. In my opinion, doing more on this matter must go. Because protecting young people from all kinds of disruptive information, preventing them from becoming zombies should be seen as a global problem.

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